

P R E S E N T A T I O N

The papers included in the present volume refer to two important scientific perspectives: *types of signs, language and interactional mechanisms of communication*, and *the social conditioning of language in general and of the literary one in particular*. Thus, the Russian researcher, **Natalia Halina** touches upon the problem of using language as a marketing structure, focusing, especially, on the mass media language. The author considers that namely this language participates in the organization of the economic life of a state.

The Romanian researcher **Ioana Boghian** examines the concept of the Victorian house as a triadic relationship from a semiotic perspective, revealing it as a space of becoming either as an icon or index or even as a symbol in the relation with its inhabitants. The author analyzes in her study a number of English novels from the XIXth century such as: „Great Expectations” and „Dombey and Son” by Ch. Dickens, the novels written by Brontë sisters and „The Return of the Native” by T. Hardy.

Lilia Răciula, a Moldovan researcher, presents an overview of the relationship *linguistic sign/poetic sign/symbol* correlating the linguistic perspective on the subject with the literary one.

Canadian Professor **Bernard Mulo Farenkia** analyzes in details a series of texts in German compiled by Cameroonians to reveal particular intercultural phenomena in them.

The Romanian researcher, **Gheorghe Săvoiu**, examines closely the notions of *enterprise, entrepreneur* and *entrepreneurship*, emphasizing the semantic contour of these terms, as well as their development during the contemporary economic crisis.

The paper of the young Romanian researcher **Ioana-Iulia Olaru** depicts briefly the way of the pictorial images from the early centuries of Christianity when these images were still considered a „*religio illicita*”. The author underlines that those artistic manifestations begin to follow some strict rules so as to render a new and surprising message.

The Romanian researcher **Lelia Trocan** considers that the definition and description of the poetic discourse from a double perspective, diachronic and synchronic, implicitly lead to a formal approach of the poetic act. In this context, the author wonders what structure and poetry are and analyzes several definitions of the mentioned phenomena suggested, especially, by the Russian formalists.

Sebastian Barth, a young German researcher, proposes a study which revalues Thomas Mann’s *Doctor Faustus* from the perspective of the social and human conditioning.

Angela Coșciug, a Moldovan researcher from Bălți, tries to explore the nature of praise and re-proof utterances in the biblical text via the pragmatic framework of the speaker’s intentions. The author underlines that these speech genres, antonymous in content and form or expression, refer, as a rule, to the factual genres, aiming at generalizing things rather than informing. These factual genres are based, first and foremost, on the evaluative semantics conditioned, in the first place, by three extralinguistic factors or components: the behavior component or the situation on the whole, the author’s component and the addressee’s component.

Ecaterina Niculcea, a young researcher from Bălți, analyzes Hoffmann’s, Gogol’s and Bulgakov’s works from the theatrical perspective, observing the fulfillment of various mime schemes in these works.

Ivan Smirnov, another researcher from Bălți, regards the language from the novel „War and Peace” by L. Tolstoy as being non-homogenous, where French lexical items play an important role and become stylistically and pragmatically marked forms.

The volume ends with some translations from the works of the greatest Romanian writer Mihai Eminescu, carried out by **Luiza Șoșu**, a translator from Bălți.